

Potentiometric Studies on the Complex Formation of Bivalent Metal Ions with *N*-Methylisatin- β -amidinohydrazone

KAKALI SARKAR and B. S. GARG*

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

Manuscript received 28 August 1984, accepted 3 June 1985

Proton-ligand formation constant of *N*-methylisatin- β -amidinohydrazone (β -MIAG) and metal-ligand formation constants of its complexes with UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Mn^{2+} have been determined at different ionic strengths (0.02, 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 *M* NaClO_4) and at different temperatures (30, 40, 45 and 50°) in 50% v/v dioxan-water medium, using Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique. The \bar{n} values ($0.1 < \bar{n} \leq 1.8$) reveal the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. The stepwise formation constants have been calculated by weighted least-squares method. The order of log *K* values of M^{2+} - β -MIAG chelates is in accordance with Irving-William's series. The thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH , ΔS and ligand field stabilisation energy, δH , of complexation reaction have been calculated from temperature coefficient data. The enthalpy changes are endothermic. The entropy is, however, positive for all the systems investigated.

THE interest in the study of hydrazones has been growing due to their use in biological system¹⁻³ and analytical chemistry⁴. The hydrazones find wide applications in the treatment of several diseases such as tuberculosis, leprosy and mental disorders⁴, and can also act as herbicides, insecticides, rodenticides and plant growth regulators^{1,5}. Although hydrazones have been most widely studied, but amidinohydrazones have not previously been studied as analytical reagent. Their chelating ability and other pharmacological activities promoted us to undertake the title investigation.

Experimental

ECIL PH-5651 digital pH meter with a single glass-calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements. It was standardised with potassium hydrogen phthalate and phosphate buffers.

N-Methylisatin- β -amidinohydrazone (β -MIAG) was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantity of *N*-methylisatin and aminoguanidine nitrate in alcohol. β -MIAG was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 210-211°. Its purity was further checked by ir, elemental analysis and tlc. Solution of the ligand was prepared in freshly distilled dioxan. All the metal ion solutions were prepared from AnalaR samples of the corresponding nitrates or sulphates and were standardised by conventional methods. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was used to keep ionic strength constant. A 0.05 *M* solution of tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH) (E. Merck, AG, Darmstadt) in 50% dioxan was used as titrant. It was standardised with a standard solution of oxalic acid. Dioxan was purified by refluxing with sodium metal for 24 h and was freshly distilled over sodium before use. All other chemicals used were

of reagent grade. Presaturated nitrogen (with 50% dioxan) was passed into the reaction solution. All measurements were made at a definite temperature ($\pm 0.5^\circ$) by using MLW (West Germany) NBE type thermostat.

Potentiometric titration: The method of Bjerrum and Calvin as modified by Irving-Rossotti^{6,7}, was used to determine \bar{n} and *pL* values. The experimental procedure involved the potentiometric titrations of the following solutions (total volume = 19.67 ml, due to contraction on mixing dioxan and water) against 0.05 *M* TMAH in 50% dioxan-water to determine \bar{n} and *pL* values of the complexes.

- (i) 1.5 ml HClO_4 (0.02 *M*) + 2.0 ml NaClO_4 (2 *M*) + 1.0 ml KNO_3 or K_2SO_4 (0.01 *M*) + 5.5 ml H_2O + 10.0 ml dioxan.
- (ii) 1.5 ml HClO_4 (0.02 *M*) + 2.0 ml NaClO_4 (2 *M*) + 1.0 ml KNO_3 or K_2SO_4 (0.01 *M*) + 5.0 ml ligand (0.01 *M*) in 50% v/v dioxan-water medium + 3.0 ml H_2O + 7.5 ml dioxan.
- (iii) 1.5 ml HClO_4 (0.02 *M*) + 2.0 ml NaClO_4 (2 *M*) + 1.0 ml metal nitrate or sulphate (0.01 *M*) + 5.0 ml ligand (0.01 *M*) in 50% v/v dioxan-water medium + 3.0 ml H_2O + 7.5 ml dioxan.

The titrations were repeated at other ionic strengths ($\mu = 0.1, 0.05$ and 0.02 *M* NaClO_4). In order to determine thermodynamic parameters, the titrations were also carried out at various temperatures (30, 40, 45 and 50°). The rapid attainment of equilibrium during titration and the absence of any significant drift in pH meter readings indicate the absence of hydrolysis in the systems.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curve of solutions (i) and (ii), \bar{n}_H values were calculated by employing the relationship derived by Irving and Rossotti. The formation curve of proton-ligand system extends over 0.1 to 0.95 indicating that only one proton dissociates from ligand molecule. The pK_1 value of the ligand was obtained by plotting $\log \bar{n}_H/(1-\bar{n}_H)$ vs pH , and the values are reported in Table 1.

by minimising $S(S = \sum_{i=1}^I (x_i y_i z_i))$ with respect to variation in β_n .

We report here the S_{min} values for respective metal complexes. S_{min} has the same statistical distribution as χ^2 with K degrees of freedom, and with weight defined in accordance with Rydberg and Sullivan⁹, we can put $S_{min} = \chi^2$.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANT OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH β -MIAG AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS
Temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$

System	Stability constant	Ionic strength ($M NaClO_4$)				
		0.2	0.1	0.05	0.02	0.00
β -MIAG	pK_1	7.650	7.950	8.150	8.350	—
UO_2^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	6.461	7.008	7.403	7.871	8.450
	$\log K_2$	5.877	6.279	6.683	6.697	—
	S_{min}	0.15304	0.13533	0.12188	0.15119	—
Cu^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	6.369	6.815	6.987	7.194	7.570
	$\log K_2$	5.257	5.413	5.838	6.082	—
	S_{min}	0.00118	0.02101	0.02854	0.08434	—
Ni^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	5.501	5.847	6.110	6.410	6.820
	$\log K_2$	4.792	5.159	5.515	5.816	—
	S_{min}	0.05735	0.05705	0.10455	0.10504	—
Pb^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	5.207	5.533	5.831	5.938	6.390
	$\log K_2$	3.936	4.225	4.527	4.591	—
	S_{min}	0.03042	0.04152	0.04570	0.12578	—
Co^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	4.944	5.303	5.598	5.868	6.290
	$\log K_2$	3.557	4.135	4.413	4.772	—
	S_{min}	0.00579	0.04584	0.08473	0.12599	—
Zn^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	4.933	5.296	5.538	5.831	6.180
	$\log K_2$	3.212	3.600	3.854	4.156	—
	S_{min}	0.01627	0.02857	0.03559	0.04162	—
Cd^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	4.146	4.463	4.801	4.992	5.390
	$\log K_2$	2.981	3.380	3.491	3.653	—
	S_{min}	0.00164	0.00957	0.02557	0.04104	—
Mn^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	3.809	4.189	4.424	4.600	4.960
	S_{min}	0.02244	0.02756	0.00836	0.01318	—

From the titration curves of solutions (i), (ii) and (iii), \bar{n} values of the metal complexes were determined at various pH values. The \bar{n} values (0.1 to 1.8) indicate the formation of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The stability constants were computed on a IBM 360 FORTRAN IV computer using a weighted least-squares programme patterned after that of Sullivan *et al.*⁹. The β_n values were initially approximated from the data (\bar{n} , pL), with weight factor being unity; second approximations to the β_n values were then calculated, by attaching to them appropriate weight factors, computed from the first set of β_n values, and the process was repeated until successive cycles gave a change of less than one part per thousand in each β_n .

The weighted least-squares treatment determines that set of β_n values which make the function $U\{U = \sum_{n=0}^N (y - x - nz) \beta_n x^n\}$ nearest to zero,

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants were calculated at four different ionic strengths (0.2, 0.1, 0.05 and 0.02 $M NaClO_4$), at four different temperatures (30, 40, 45 and 50°), at constant ionic strength, and the values are recorded in Tables 1 and 2. The thermodynamic parameters ΔG , ΔH and ΔS have been calculated by using the following relationships¹⁰ and values are given in Table 3.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G &= -RT \ln K \\ d \log K / d(1/T) &= \Delta H / 2.303R \\ \Delta S &= (\Delta H - \Delta G) / T \end{aligned}$$

It is evident from Table 1 that the stability constants of the complexes follow the order found by Mellor and Maley^{11,12} and Irving and Williams^{13,14}. The sequence found out to be $UO_2 > Cu > Ni > Pb > Co > Zn > Cd > Mn$. In all the cases, the values of $\log K_1 > \log K_2$. The differences, $\log K_1 - \log K_2$, for the various metal

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH β -MIAG AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

$\mu = 0.1 M NaClO_4$

System	Stability constant	Temp. °C		
		40	45	50
β -MIAG	pK_1	8.090	8.160	8.220
UO_2^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	7.239	7.433	7.555
	$\log K_2$	6.314	6.713	6.964
	S_{min}	0.37975	0.12189	0.02449
Cu^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	7.037	7.086	7.221
	$\log K_2$	5.588	5.976	6.099
	S_{min}	0.03494	0.29005	0.11732
Ni^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	6.065	6.183	6.152
	$\log K_2$	5.230	5.415	5.478
	S_{min}	0.01241	0.11849	0.02001
Pb^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	5.801	5.806	5.816
	$\log K_2$	4.540	4.584	4.594
	S_{min}	0.03982	0.07658	0.07659
Co^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	5.498	5.659	5.732
	$\log K_2$	4.314	4.578	4.370
	S_{min}	0.08348	0.15522	0.15522
Zn^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	5.392	5.508	5.660
	$\log K_2$	3.702	3.823	3.860
	S_{min}	0.03157	0.03484	0.06099
Cd^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	4.683	4.788	5.037
	$\log K_2$	3.419	3.631	3.859
	S_{min}	0.00746	0.01182	0.01365
Mn^{2+} - β -MIAG	$\log K_1$	4.534	4.534	4.817
	S_{min}	0.01044	0.01044	0.02022

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF BIVALENT METAL COMPLEXES WITH β -MIAG

$\mu = 0.1 M NaClO_4$, Temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$

System	$-\Delta G$	ΔH	ΔS
	kcal mol ⁻¹	kcal mol ⁻¹	cal mol ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹
UO_2^{2+} - β -MIAG	9.717	10.054	65.251
	(8.706)	(3.661)	(40.815)
Cu^{2+} - β -MIAG	9.450	8.008	57.617
	(7.506)	(5.949)	(44.406)
Ni^{2+} - β -MIAG	8.108	9.381	57.719
	(7.153)	(3.432)	(34.934)
Pb^{2+} - β -MIAG	7.672	9.839	57.792
	(5.858)	(11.440)	(57.089)
Co^{2+} - β -MIAG	7.353	9.152	54.472
	(5.733)	(8.237)	(46.106)
Zn^{2+} - β -MIAG	7.342	6.406	45.373
	(4.992)	(5.949)	(36.109)
Cd^{2+} - β -MIAG	6.188	9.381	51.383
	(4.686)	(2.745)	(24.525)
Mn^{2+} - β -MIAG	5.807	9.610	50.881

Values in parantheses are for the reactions involving formation of 1 : 2 complexes.

complexes studied do not indicate a purely statistical addition of second ligand. The differences observed have shown no definite trend and it seems probable that the cation is so modified by the addition of first ligand, that the forces leading to the interaction of singly charged 1 : 1 complex with second molecule of ligand are of quite different

type and order from those operating between the solvated metal ion and the first molecule of ligand.

Fig. 1. Plots of relative values of ΔH_H and ΔH_L against the number of 3d electrons for β -MIAG complexes.

The effect of ionic strength on these metal-ligand stability constant has been found to be parallel to pK_1 of β -MIAG. This is in agreement with the Debye-Hückel¹⁵ equation.

The Arrhenius plots ($\log K$ vs $1/T$) have been drawn for the complexes of β -MIAG with bivalent metal ions at different temperatures in the range $30-50^\circ$ at $0.1 M NaClO_4$. From the slopes of these plots, the thermodynamic parameters have been computed (Table 3). The results indicate that ΔG is negative, which shows that complex formation reactions take place spontaneously. The enthalpy

TABLE 4— $Er(Mn-Zn)$ AND δH VALUES FOR COMPLEXES OF β -MIAG

Parameters	Metal ions				
	Mn^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}
$\log K_1^0$	4.960	6.290	6.820	7.570	6.180
ΔF	6.877	8.721	9.456	10.496	8.569
ΔF_R	-	1.844	2.579	3.619	1.692
ΔH_H	-	43.000	62.000	63.000	47.000
ΔH_L	-	44.844	64.579	66.619	48.692
$[(n-5)/5]Er$	-	19.477	29.215	38.954	-
δH	-	25.367	35.364	27.665	-

ΔF = Free energy change = $2.303 RT \log K_1^0$, where R , T and K_1^0 have usual significance and temp. = $303^\circ K$; ΔF_R = change in heat content for the formation of the complex in solution; ΔH_H = heat of hydration of metal ion; ΔH_L = heat of complexation referred to metal ion in gaseous and ligand in solution state; n = number of electrons in 3d orbital; $[(n-5)/5]Er$ = lattice energy difference for Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} complexes; δH = thermodynamic stabilization energy; $\log K_1^0$ = values employed for the above calculations, obtained by extrapolating the $\log K_1$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ (straight line) to zero ionic strength.

changes for the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 M^{II} - β -MIAG systems are endothermic. In spite of these unfavourable enthalpy changes the complexes are stabilised by relatively large positive entropy change. The thermodynamic formation constants were evaluated by extrapolating the concentration stability constants to zero ionic strength and the values are given in Table 1.

The ligand field stabilisation energy (δH) and $E_r(\text{Mn-Zn})$ values have been calculated according to the method of George and McClure¹⁶ and are listed in Table 4. The order of ligand field stabilisation energy (δH) is, $\text{Co} < \text{Ni} > \text{Cu}$.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (K.S.).

References

1. J. F. ALCOCK, R. J. BAKER and A. A. DIAMANTIS, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1972, 25, 289.
2. J. R. DILWORTH, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1976, 21, 29.
3. N. SAHA and D. BHATTACHARYYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 143.
4. M. KATYAL and Y. DUTT, *Talanta*, 1975, 22, 151.
5. R. C. AGGARWAL, B. N. YADAV and T. PRASAD, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, 35, 653.
6. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
8. J. C. SULLIVAN, J. RYDBERG and W. E. MILLER, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1959, 13, 2023.
9. J. RYDBERG and J. C. SULLIVAN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1959, 13, 2057.
10. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASILEV, "Instability Constants of Complex Compounds", Pergamon Press, New York, 1960.
11. D. P. MELLOR and L. MALEY, *Nature (London)*, 1947, 159, 370.
12. D. P. MELLOR and L. MALEY, *Nature (London)*, 1948, 161, 436.
13. H. M. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature (London)*, 1948, 162, 746.
14. H. M. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192.
15. R. NASANEN and A. EKMAN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, 6, 1389.
16. P. GEORGE and D. S. MCCLURE, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1959, 1, 428.